

PUNTO CRÍTICO

NOVEMBER - DECEMBER 2023
ISSUE 8

Me
CCS
PLATAFORMA MEXICANA
DE CAPTURA Y
ALMACENAMIENTO
DE CO₂

PUNTO CRÍTICO

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CDMX, México.

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10137899

Editor's note

America's tapestry – or it is probably better to say Abya Yala and the Turtle Island – is intertwined with threads of multiple narratives, traditions and struggles. This territory, of course, is not only an area of 18 million square kilometers, but a space where worlds, visions and epistemes come together. Undoubtedly, plurality and the inherent human and ecological wealth constitute a critical point concerning biodiversity, heritage, social and political movements, spirituality and philosophies of life that are central in debates on rights, equity and social justice. Therefore, the inhabitants of this continent have a crucial role in facing the socio-environmental challenges of which, consciously or unconsciously, we are a part.

In this issue, we present an article by Jazmín Mota from MeCCS about the encounter of worlds, knowledge and technologies in Latin America and the human-nature interconnections that allow us to outline and trace alternatives towards sustainability. Tatiana, Rocío and Gianella Espinosa, founders of the Association for the Resilience of the Forest against the Inter-Oceanic (ARBIO), share their vision, experience and challenges in the conservation work of the Amazon forest. In the *CO₂nversing* section, we include an interview with Daniel Patiño about the first hydrogen car in Latin America. In the *Yes, yes it is* section, we show relevant information about America through some maps. Finally, in *Take Away*, we compile some books, documentaries and projects to deepen our continent's knowledge and challenges in socio-environmental issues.

Globalization and technology

Throughout history, six significant globalization waves have occurred, marked by the development of technology (agricultural, military, naval, information technology, etc.), the physical environment (geomorphology, natural resources, climate), demography, wars and conquests, ideologies (culture, language, rules), political and cultural institutions. Although all of these factors have been fundamental, I will focus on technology.

Technology is a set of techniques and skills that have allowed humanity to produce tools, goods and services. It has been a critical element in the development of civilizations and the transformation of the environment – and, with it, our ways of life. One of them was, for instance, the use of fire, which modified our way of defending ourselves and our diet. According to the Smithsonian Institute, some of the earliest evidence of the use of fire for cooking food can date back more than 1.5 million years. And, like this example, we can find great leaps that have occurred in the history of humanity thanks to innovation and the spread of technology.

In many places in the world, evidence of sophisticated technologies such as hydraulic and sanitary systems, architectural structures, road networks, instruments for observing the stars and monitoring natural phenomena, and significant advances in medicine and agriculture have been found, to name a few. Such was the case of civilizations in Abya Yala, such as the Mayan, the Aztecs and the Inca, where there were also highly specialized people who dedicated their lives to science and the arts, contributing their knowledge to the sustainability of their societies.

With the conquest of Abya Yala, a fusion was made not only between people but also in ways of life, techniques and practices in a multilateral sense. The elements of nature, indigenous knowledge and their techniques permeated Europe through the stories of the conquerors and chroniclers. Little by little, the use of iron and the wheel was adopted in America, and new plants and animals were introduced. On the other hand, Europeans learned agricultural techniques to grow crops in different climates and environments, such as jungles, lakes and semi-deserts. The virtues of the plants used in indigenous medicine were used in Europe, as presented by Agustín Farfán, doctor to Philip II, in his book *Tractado de anathomía y chirugía*. If we want, the list of examples can continue.

Between the 15th and 17th centuries, the conquests gave way to what is known as the triangular trade, where raw materials from America were imported to Europe to be manufactured and then taken to Africa, where, in turn, they were traded with people in the slave markets, which were later taken to America to work in the fields and the mines, not only for their physical strength (as we have been historically taught) but for the valuable knowledge and technology African people had.

This time was characterized by exacerbated abuses, impunity, and overexploitation of people and resources, and also by an intense exchange of techniques, knowledge and technologies between the three regions. Any resemblance to today? Probably yes.

⁴ Indigenous science:
https://dhial.org/diccionario/index.php?title=CIENCIA_Y_TECNOLOG%C3%8DA_EN_LA_HISTORIA_DE_AM%C3%89RICA#La_ciencia_ind.C3.ADgena

The worlds, knowledge and technologies encounter

Today, we are still immersed in a trade network (no longer just a triangle) where we have a constant exchange of knowledge, techniques, methods and technologies that continuously adapt, modify and provide feedback. Furthermore, we are excited by the technocracy, which makes us think that technology is THE solution to the socio-environmental and economic problems that we have unleashed and sustained for centuries.

However, technology is a tool that depends on who uses it and what they use it for. However, we lose the direction of the fact that many of these technologies are developed to alleviate the significant effects and impacts that we cause (or at least that is what we should be heading towards). If we are aware of this, then we can strive to construct a world where - as the Zapatistas say - many worlds fit.

In this rapidly changing world, we need the experience, creativity, ingenuity and knowledge of those who develop and apply technology, and also the participation of those who will be affected or benefited by its implementation. Returning to the idea of integral ecology, we need to understand the interconnections between nature and society and, if we go one step further, expand our understanding of worldviews and cultures where we seek to introduce alternatives to alleviate sustainability problems, as well as be attentive to not addressing global problems, forgetting about local effects and needs.

Thus, we arrive at a time when we have a series of nature and technology-based alternatives for decarbonization in Latin America and various models and routes towards sustainability. However, to avoid repeating some historical mistakes, these options must be well understood, evaluated, provided with feedback and - in many cases - reinvented from the local vision and contexts. Indeed, the collaboration and accompaniment of those who already have a path travelled is valuable and must be seen from a decolonial perspective as a dialogue among peers, where the technique, creativity and ingenuity of all parties co-exist and co-construct local solutions that contribute to solving global problems.

The Amazon Forest: sustenance and resilience

By **Tatiana, Rocío y Gianella Espinosa**

ARBIO (Association for Forest Resilience against the Inter-Oceanic Highway) is an organization created in 2010 to protect an area of natural forest located 20 km away from the interoceanic highway that began operating in 2011. Its founders, Tatiana and Rocío Espinosa, were joined by Gianella a few years later. Today, it is the three sisters who lead this initiative in a forestry concession granted for 40 years that, voluntarily, they requested a change to a conservation concession in 2019. In the project, they carry out conservation and protection activities in the 916 hectares (2 200 acres) of natural forest under their care, where destruction threats increase every day.

The Guardians of the Forest

To obtain a professional degree in Forest Engineering, Tatiana did research that led her to enter the jungle of Madre de Dios, in the southeast of Peru, where she had her first contact and deep immersion in the forest. Years later, she developed professional activities in the field, acquiring the experience and confidence to request a forest area in concession due to the urgency of protecting it since the construction of the interoceanic highway would negatively impact the region. It is in this area where ARBIO's conservation activities are currently carried out.

Rocío has a bachelor's degree in Food Industry Engineering and a master's in Business Administration. Her experience comes from the private sector: industrial, banking and investments. In the years before starting ARBIO, she worked for an environmental consulting firm. Gianella is a professional photographer with a bachelor's degree in audiovisual media. The three of them lead the organization, coordinating field operations with their team of rangers to maintain the ecosystem and promote a shared conservation model for the local benefit and the entire planet.

In 2019, Tatiana won the international "Jane Goodall. Hope and Inspiration Ranger Award", awarded by the International Ranger Federation (IRF), the Thin Green Line organization and the International Union for Conservation of Nature / World Commission of Protected Areas (IUCN/WCPA).

This recognition was granted in Nepal during the World Park Ranger Congress for the forest conservation and defence work that Jane Goodall, an IRF ambassador who permanently supports people dedicated to protecting nature, has organized since 2010 with her organization and team of rangers.

The Amazon Forest and the Selective Logging of Ancient Trees

In Madre de Dios, there are areas where mining is the leading cause of deforestation, while in the Las Piedras River basin, where the ARBIO forest is located, selective logging of hardwood trees is the first link in the deforestation chain. The first step in forest degradation and deforestation is, in particular, the extraction of the Shihuahuaco (*Dipteryx* spp.), one of the tallest ancient trees in the Amazon forest, which can reach up to 60 meters in height.

To better understand the problem, let's discuss the difference between the terms 'degradation' and 'deforestation'. Deforestation occurs when portions of the Amazon forest are razed, leaving gaps in the jungle that can be seen from aeroplanes and satellite images. Degradation is almost invisible, imperceptible to satellites or from aerial views. Degradation occurs, for example, when the selective logging of large trees, such as the Shihuahuaco, that support the ecosystem occurs.

Today, we know that the degradation of forests and natural ecosystems emits almost as much greenhouse gases (GHG) as deforestation itself. In addition, it implies the loss of biodiversity and humidity, reduces the ecological functions of the forest (ecosystem services) and causes a greater risk of fires to prevail. The main cause of forest degradation is selective logging for timber extraction or removing trees from timber species of commercial interest. It has caused the "commercial extinctions" of species such as rosewood, romerillo, mahogany, lupuna, screw, ishpingo, and now shihuahuaco – the preferred wood of the Chinese market.

The slow natural growth rate of the *Dipteryx ferrea* species, as well as several species of hardwood and emergent trees (the tallest because they “emerge” above the forest canopy), makes their use unsustainable. In addition, these trees have essential characteristics:

- They **provide food and nesting** for a wide variety of bird species, such as macaws, parrots and the imposing harpy eagle;
- Its **carbon capture capacity is one of the highest** of Amazonian trees;
- They have **an important role in the Amazon ecosystem** as an emerging and long-lived species;
- They have **a high scientific value**, being standing trees that are more than 500 or 1000 years old.

For all of the above, it can be stated that the shihuahuaco (also commercially called cumarú) has enough reasons to be a species with high conservation value. However, little was known about its life cycle, despite being number one in Peruvian wood exports in recent years.

Tatiana Espinosa led the research of the shihuahuaco and, in 2020, along with Biol. Daniel Valle published a paper that demonstrates the unsustainability of the use (logging) of shihuahuaco from the natural forest for commercial use as wood. The conclusions of the ARBIO natural forest study were that:

68% of the shihuahuaco trees have more than 500 years; 16% more than 1000 years.

A shihuahuaco takes around 322 years to grow 51 cm in diameter (minimum felling diameter).

The population density in this area is 0.7 shihuahuacos / hectare.

Since the publication of these results, ARBIO has been spreading the urgency of stopping the felling of these giant trees. It is now known that trees over 500 years old are cut down to be used as floors, and consequently, no new plantation will be able to replace them.

The Peruvian forestry industry extracts wood from natural forests. Forest plantations in Peru are scarce, and there are no forests that humans have planted with trees like the shihuahuaco that are already mature enough for logging. **The big problem is that extracting hardwood from natural forests is legal.** There are only some protected species that cannot be cut down, such as the Amazonian chestnut tree (*Bertholletia excelsa*), due to the importance of the harvest of its nuts for the economy of chestnut-growing communities in the region.

¹ Evaluación poblacional de *Dipteryx micrantha* en la cuenca del río Las Piedras, Madre de Dios (Perú). Tatiana Espinosa y Daniel Valle (2020). Revista Forestal del Perú. Vol. 35 Núm.3: Número Especial. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21704/rfp.v35i3.1603>

The flying rivers

Did you know that the large Amazonian trees not only capture CO₂ and provide us with oxygen to live? They also act as gigantic water pumps.

They absorb water from the subsoil through their roots and carry it to their branches and leaves, where evapotranspiration occurs, causing moisture to be transported into the atmosphere. All this mass of water joins with the evaporation of the Atlantic Ocean, forming a **“flying river”**, a large flow of atmospheric moisture that can transport more water than the Amazon River itself.

This impressive process **occurs through the more than 300 billion trees that exist in the Amazon, each of them with the capacity to send approximately 1,000 liters of water per day into the atmosphere.** This flow of water flies at incredible speeds over the Amazon forest until it reaches the Andes Mountains, against which it collides and, in this way, feeds its snow-capped mountains and glaciers where the melting happens, forming the rivers and valleys of the Pacific coast. Thanks to the flying rivers, there are water reserves from which the coast and the South American mountains benefit.

ARBIO: a fragile ecosystem

Fragile ecosystems are areas of high conservation value, with a great richness in species of wild flora and fauna, and habitats in a good state of conservation that provide ecosystem services for the benefit of the local population. Threatened and endemic species are also found there. In 2020, the ARBIO forest was recognized as one of the fragile ecosystems of Madre de Dios by the National Forestry and Wildlife Service (SERFOR) of the Ministry of Agrarian Development, joining the list of 154 fragile ecosystems in Peru.

With this categorization of the ARBIO forest, with a significant conservation value, it was expected that regional and local authorities would have special management for its protection, implying the execution of control, supervision, inspection and forest surveillance actions. However, three years have passed, and the forest is still threatened by the impunity of illegal activities that advance daily in the region. The fragility of these ecosystems should not strengthen illegality and corruption but rather attract opportunities for collaboration, research, strengthening and growth in the region.

Suppose the destruction of the forest is not stopped. In that case, we will reach a point of no return that would imply the collapse of the Amazon ecosystems and a process of savanna that would also affect flying rivers and significantly impact access to water. There would be an irreparable loss of biodiversity, significant modifications in water and carbon cycles, the acceleration of climate change and its consequences as climate disasters, and many communities that depend on the forest and its resources for their livelihood. In an interconnected world, local impacts have a substantial effect (positive or negative) at a global level. For this reason, it is vitally important to inform ourselves and take action.

Join us!

ARBIO invites you to join this work to protect and study the primary forests of the Peruvian Amazon that still survive. A simple way to contribute is by adopting an ancient tree to commemorate something significant or as a gift of life, consciousness and collective effort for a better planet. If you are part of a company or the private sector, you can also participate and strengthen your commitment to environmental sustainability.

Visit the ARBIO website to learn more about the project and how to join the initiative to preserve the forest: www.arbioperu.org

CQ₂ NVERSING

If the river sounds, it is because hydrogen flows: the first H₂-based car in Latin America

Interview with **Daniel Patiño, OPEX S.A.S,**
By **Lorena Morales y Mariana Velázquez**

We are at a critical moment in which we must find alternatives to many local needs and global problems that suddenly come at full speed in a race against time. One of the issues of modernity on which high expectations are placed is hydrogen as a transitional and clean fuel. There are many ways to produce and use it, and developing technologies for its production and use is becoming increasingly ambitious. Some countries in Europe, Asia and North America have invested significant amounts in this issue; in these regions, many economic resources and institutional and political structures promote them.

But also, the ingenuity and enormous problem-solving capacity in Latin America positions Colombia as the first country in the region to have a hydrogen production plant that powers the first hydrogen-based car that circulates on Medellín roads.

Undoubtedly, this project is a clear example that thinking about a different world and alternatives is possible, and even better, these worlds can be built and inhabited. How do we achieve it? We just need creativity, imagination and collaboration because, in Abya Yala, everything is possible. In an interview with Daniel Patiño, we tell you the story of this project planted in a fertile land in Antioquia, Colombia, where, little by little, we see new and great ideas flourish.

Daniel Patiño is a mechanical engineer from the University of Antioquia whose work has focused on the technical-commercial and engineering areas. Throughout his career, he has worked on the analysis of testbed engines and alternative low-emission fuels. His interest and curiosity in automobiles arose as a child, motivated by his father's work in the car assembly industry. This passion is also reflected in the alternative energy projects he has proactively participated in. His experience has led him to delve into the impacts that the development of new technologies and innovations has on people and the environment. Currently, he is the technical manager at OPEX S.A.S, a company that, together with HEVOLUTION, developed the first car with a green hydrogen engine put into circulation on Medellín roads, where he is from.

Vehículo de hidrógeno

L: Daniel, please tell us, how did the idea of creating a hydrogen-based car and, furthermore, running on green hydrogen come about?

D: It all starts at **OPEX S.A.S**, a company that sells and rents batteries for forklifts that have been in the market for 12 years. Our manager, Diego Arboleda, was at a conference in the United States when he observed that forklifts required three conventional batteries that take up to 8 hours to charge, in contrast to hydrogen ones that do so in just 3 minutes. This energy potential of hydrogen, in contrast to other fuels, was the beginning of the project.

Once in Colombia, and with the idea of using hydrogen as fuel that Diego brought, we began to do a complete investigation on the prices of hydrogen in the country. We found that the cost per kilogram was approximately \$280, making it unaffordable. In addition, many questions arose about hydrogen generation, use and management and the main challenges we could face. It is how **HEVOLUTION** was born, as OPEX's spin-off designed to address the issue of green hydrogen production.

As you know, hydrogen has been given many “*last names*” that refer to the sources from which it is produced. It can be grey, blue, turquoise, or green, depending on the emissions generated in its production. For our project, the best alternative was green hydrogen generated from renewable energies. Then, we analyzed **what type of technologies we could use**. We have many water sources in Colombia, so we chose to build a small hydroelectric plant, which does not imply the creation of large reservoirs and all their negative impacts. The plant generates 20 megawatts using approximately 70% of the energy. This energy is generated constantly compared to other intermittent energy such as solar and wind. In terms of price, producing hydrogen with the technology we selected is only 10% of the cost of solar or wind energy.

The next step was to “**assemble**” all the pieces through a strategy to attract investments to our project. We brought a car to Colombia that runs on locally produced hydrogen so that people could see it, get in it and see how it works. This car has tremendous autonomy; with 9 liters of water, we produce 1 kilogram of hydrogen and can travel 150km. The hydrogen enters fuel-cell membranes where it combines with oxygen, generating a lot of energy, and the product of this process is water vapor. Tanking the car takes 5 minutes, and we have 660 km of autonomy, one of the most efficient options.

M: Without a doubt, this project has many advantages, but what would you say are the disadvantages or challenges of this technology?

D: First, the **economic aspect**. If we have a truck that runs 90% on diesel and I want to replace the other 10% with green hydrogen, the cost of that hydrogen is between 10-17 dollars. For this replacement exercise to work, the cost of hydrogen would have to be 5-6 dollars. On the other hand, when hydrogen is produced, it is done at a very low, almost atmospheric pressure, but to **transport** it, you can do three things: first, you can compress it, although a lot of energy is needed for this process; second, they can liquefy it at cryogenic temperatures to increase its density and be able to transport a more significant quantity; third, you can convert it into ammonia (NH₃) with a process called Haber-Bosch in which a larger molecule is formed and transported in a liquid state, then in the place where the hydrogen is required, the through cracking hydrogens and nitrates are separated. This last process has an additional benefit: nitrates can be used for fertilizers, which, for Colombia, is an excellent thing since the country produces only 5% of the fertilizers it uses.

M: And in the social aspect, what kind of impact is on the communities, or what is their involvement like?

D: In one of the planned projects, some indigenous communities are dedicated to growing and harvesting coffee. For us, our activities mustn't affect the flow and access of water that they need. Additionally, our team includes anthropologists and sociologists as well as engineers. They are in charge of monitoring and following up on the communities. We have also involved people at the local level through their training and integration into the project. Regarding water, we are cautious since we cannot put this resource at risk, and, for its part, the current government is very strict with these situations, something with which we agree entirely.

It is worth saying that our project also collaborates with the University of Antioquia, which plays a critical role in continuous improvement and joint work in the region, and they also support us in the anthropological aspects and raising awareness with the government.

L: How necessary is it to encourage innovation in Colombia, and how can this technology spread to the rest of Latin America?

D: In the country, there are many, many ideas. People have a lot of excellent knowledge. Encouraging or incentivizing would not be the word I would use now; for me, it is more important to **structure** an environment, policies and conditions that allow this type of project to be promoted.

Of course, working together is also essential. Although each company has its know-how and professional secrets, all this must **be shared with** the student community and the corporate part. It is how we combine the experience and talk about the mistakes, and everything experienced along the way.

In our plans, there is the idea of developing projects outside the country. We have made significant progress in collaboration with Panama and Peru and are in talks with other countries where hydraulic energy can be used as a critical aspect. In the long term, we want to expand these projects in Colombia and Latin America to scale them and bring them to the adoption level.

We know that at the moment, hydrogen cannot replace other forms of energy but will instead be a complementary element that will gradually **transition** towards less polluting fuels. Today, a conventional 40-ton diesel vehicle costs \$150,000, while a hydrogen vehicle with the same characteristics would cost \$600,000, so a company will prefer conventional vehicles. That's the challenge!

L: Finally, can these projects strengthen and unite us as a region?

D: Of course, yes. Although there are significant differences with other countries regarding the budget allocated to education and research, **we are very resourceful and inventive in Latin America**. For example, a man in Cuba, where there are no spare parts and must repair his car, can do so with the resources he has at hand, even without having studied a degree or being a specialist in the subject. I think that the intelligence and ability of Latin people is enormous. All we need is to be **more disciplined and unselfish** to share what we know with others genuinely. This way, we can build synergies between different countries and make great progress in our proposal. We have everything: the technology and the ability to develop and do many things. It is **a matter of will** because engineering and knowledge already exist. Still, these issues are very political, which is difficult to modify, but we must do it. Let there be no doubt that we are very well prepared and have many tools to solve and achieve what we set out to do.

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

The upside-down world... ¿or the other way around?

Have you wondered how the orientation of the maps is decided and if it has any effect or reason?

According to some research, the way we “see” things has a psychological effect and a message behind it. In the case of maps, there is an association and connotation regarding its position (north or up=good, south or down=bad).

To decode this idea (more than erroneous) we can use **south-up maps** which, believe it or not, are nothing new. The use of maps with a different orientation can be found in the early 1900s, when **Joaquín Torres García, a Uruguayan painter**, placed the south pole at the top of the image, making a suggestive statement of the importance of South America.

Another important contribution was that of the **“Universal Corrective Map of the World”**, by Stuart McArthur (1979), to note that the prestige and “superiority” of northern countries over those of the global south seems predetermined by their spatial position.

Concepts such as “developed and developing”, “upper class and lower class”, among many others, should be obsolete, but unfortunately they are more than current.

One more reference to this spatial idea is the **Epistemologies of the South**, where the reference to the **Global North and South** is used. Its proponent, Boaventura de Sousa Santos, explains that our “position” in sociopolitical systems has a direct implication in the realities in which we live and the multiple inequalities and social and environmental problems we face.

Quino, the famous Argentine cartoonist, creator of Mafalda, already stated it: **“space has neither up nor down.”**

Let's see some interesting facts on maps about this upside down world...

The carbon footprint: another way to measure inequality

World map of accumulated CO2 emissions from 1970 to 2021.

45% of historical CO2 emissions come from **developed countries** and **24% from developing countries in Asia and the Pacific** (a region that includes countries with high emissions in the last 50 years, such as China and India).

The rest:
 Eastern Europe and Central and Western Asia (11%)
Latin America and the Caribbean (11%)
 Africa (7%)
 Middle East (2%).

United States, China and Russia are the largest emitters of CO2 over time.

According to the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), **Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC)** is **one of the regions in the world most affected by climate change and extreme weather events**, which are causing serious damage to health, life, food security, access to water, energy and socioeconomic development in the region.

It is important to reflect on the actions that high-emission countries are taking, not only at the national level, but also at the regional and global scales, to mitigate these effects.

Sources:
<https://www.statista.com/chart/28725/cumulative-co2-emissions-per-country-since-1970/>
<https://public.wmo.int/es/estado-del-clima-en-am%C3%A9rica-latina-y-el-caribe-2022>
<https://cambioclimatico.gob.mx/cambio-climatico-america-latina-sera-una-de-las-regiones-mas-afectadas/>
<https://scioteca.caf.com/bitstream/handle/123456789/2089/RED2023-RE-ESP.pdf?sequence=20&isAllowed=y>

Biodiversity and socioenvironmental conflicts

In Latin America and the Caribbean

Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) is one of the most biologically rich regions on the planet. However, this area is influenced by socio-environmental problems that have caused impacts to the region.

Biodiversity

LAC is a region with high biodiversity wealth:

- 60%** of global terrestrial life and diverse marine and freshwater species.
- 34%** of the primary forests of the planet.
- 51%** of amphibians.
- 41%** of birds.
- 27%** of fresh water available in the world.
- 50%** of the plant life found in the Caribbean does not occur in any other area of the planet.

Socioenvironmental conflicts

LAC experiences socio-environmental problems among which are:

In 2022, **9 out of 10** of defender murders of the environment and the Earth. **39%** of them were against indigenous residents.

The region is going through the **worst migration crisis** in its history.

17 million of people could be forced to leave their homes due to hurricanes, floods and droughts, which are becoming more frequent.

5.8 million of people in the region would fall into extreme poverty by 2030, largely due to a lack of clean water, as well as increased exposure to excessive heat and flooding.

Sources:

- <https://www.bancomundial.org/es/region/lac/overview#1>
- <https://www.cepal.org/es/temas/biodiversidad/fortalezas-desafios-regionales>
- <https://www.cbd.int/gbo/gbo4/outlook-grulac-en.pdf>
- <https://www.cepal.org/es/publicaciones/48985-panorama-recursos-naturales-america-latina-caribe-2023-resumen-ejecutivo>
- <https://www.nrdc.org/es/bio/jessica-carey-webb/biodiversidad-america-latina-es-critica>
- <https://www.globalwitness.org/es/comunicados-de-prensa/almost-2000-environmental-defenders-killed-between-2012-and-2022-protecting-planet-es/>

Energy and mineral resources in Latin America and the Caribbean

Latin America and the Caribbean is a **net exporter region of natural resources**, particularly biomass and minerals. Since 2015, it has become a **net importer of fossil fuels**.

In the period 2019-2021, combined regional **exports of natural resources** represented **50.7% of total exports and 10.1% of the region's GDP**.

LAC has at their stewardship:

- 20%** of oil reserves
- 25%** of strategic metals of the world

... it seems like we live in an upside-down world where globalization, colonization and many false expectations have created great inequalities that have strongly degraded land, resources and culture.

Sources:
<https://www.cepal.org/es/publicaciones/48985-panorama-recursos-naturales-america-latina-caribe-2023-resumen-ejecutivo>
<https://portalenergetico.org/es/>

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

In this space, we compile some voices from Abya Yala, manifested in the form of documentaries, books and projects, whose objective is to delve both into the kaleidoscope of knowledge that emanates from this territory and into the complex socio-environmental conflicts of which it is a part. Likewise, we add links to events and associations that might interest you.

Call for papers: *Latin American CCUS Conference, Brazil 2024*

We invite you to review the call for papers for the Latin American CCUS Conference 2024 in Rio de Janeiro. The multidisciplinary program will include oral and poster presentations. More information in the following link:

<https://ccusevent.org/latinamerica/2024/program/technical-program>

Arbio Peru Project: *Adopt an ancient tree*

Learn about the Arbio Peru project, whose objective is the conservation of the trees and forests of the Peruvian Amazon. One of the ways to participate in this project and initiative is by "adopting" an ancient tree in danger of illegal logging. Visit the Arbio website for more information:

<https://www.arbioperu.org/adopta-un-arbol/>

Documentary: *The curse of abundance*

This documentary addresses what happens when money and morality clash to influence decision-making in the Yasuní Park in the Ecuadorian Amazon, a paradise of biodiversity where several indigenous communities live and which constitutes a space where some of the largest oil reserves in that country are.

<https://www.primevideo.com/detail/La-maldici%C3%B3n-de-la-abundancia/0GI0KBK6CNUT2AU56ZJPOVQUA8>

Documentary: *Latin America: The false myth of clean energy*

This documentary raises the voice about how the "development" discourse has served to promote extractive projects and megaprojects implemented without the consent of local communities.

<https://avispa.org/latinoamerica-el-falso-mito-de-las-energias-limpias/>

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

Book: *Rethinking sustainability from the humanities and social sciences. Definitions, problems and views from Latin America*

This book by Dora García and Margo Echenberg introduces several sustainability-related problems and complexities from a multidisciplinary perspective. It is an anthology designed as a reference book to motivate reflection on topics such as peace, education, the economy, and gender equality.

https://www.elsotano.com/libro/repensando-la-sostenibilidad-desde-las-humanidades-y-las-ciencias-sociales-definiciones-problemas-y-miradas-desde-latinoamerica_105443
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Book: *For a healthy environment that promotes human rights in the Global South*

César Rodríguez presents this book derived from the Global Action Research Workshop for Young Human Rights Defenders. In it, he detects how, with the alibi of growth or innovation, a complex global network is at the base of disasters, such as the development of megaprojects whose impact is not measured, the pressures for the adoption and use of certain agrochemicals, and other problems that it is urgent to attend, particularly in countries of the Global South.

<https://www.gandhi.com.mx/por-un-medio-ambiente-sano-que-promueva-los-derechos-humanos-en-el-sur-global>

Colombian Association of Energy Geologists and Geophysicists

The ACGGP is a non-profit entity that fosters and strengthens personal, technical and social relationships between professionals linked to Earth Sciences and related areas by promoting interdisciplinary research and disseminating knowledge in Colombian communities. Learn more about their work at the following link:

<https://www.acgpp.org/>

Book: *Heads up: an almost universal story*

From the illustrious Uruguayan writer Eduardo Galeano, this book suggests that we live in an upside-down world, with the left on the right, the navel on the back and the head on the feet. In its pages, the past and the present come together, reflecting the significant inconsistencies and ironies in the history of humanity.

https://resistir.info/livros/galeano_patas_arriba.pdf

Mexico City, Mexico, 2023